

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Quantified ex- post impacts of trade in sea biomass on biodiversity

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A significant share of sea biomass – particularly fishmeal and fish oil – feeds the aquaculture sector. The production of both fisheries and aquaculture is highly concentrated, creating complex international trade interdependencies that link aquaculture expansion to biodiversity threats in both marine and terrestrial ecosystems. As the aquaculture sector remains relevant to global food systems and its demand for sea biomass continues to grow, promoting sustainable aquaculture production (and expansion) becomes essential to mitigating its associated biodiversity risks. Achieving this requires the participation of both governments and non-government actors. Governments should continue to support their domestic aquaculture industries while ensuring that the aquatic products available in their markets meet robust social and environmental standards. At the same time, non-government actors can provide incentives to aquaculture producers to adopt sustainable production practices. This report thus explores the roles of two trade-related measures, regulatory standard-like non-tariff measures (NTMs) and voluntary market-based aquaculture sustainability certification. Together, these two measures capture how the imports and exports of aquaculture-related biomass are governed, with NTMs regulating access to domestic markets and sustainability certification influencing production practices in export-oriented supply chains.

We first assess standard-like NTMs at the country level. To protect consumer health and safety, importing countries tend to impose regulations on aquatic foods from overseas, such as testing, labelling, and certification requirements that include detailed information on ingredients, net quantity, production methods, and antimicrobial residue levels. Some NTMs also address environmental risks (e.g., invasive species) or safeguard global common resources (e.g., protected endangered species of wild fauna and flora). These measures may influence domestic producers by altering domestic market dynamics via changing consumer demand for higher-quality and safer products, or as unintentional side effects of protectionist policies. We ask whether these NTMs implemented by importing countries hinder their domestic aquaculture producers, thus reinforcing the existing geographical unevenness in global aquatic product trade. We then borrow the aquaculture development archetype framework by Partelow et al. (2025) to contextualize how these impacts vary across countries' differences in economic, environmental, and governance dimensions. As these country groups have various aquatic farmed biodiversity types (e.g., brackish, marine, freshwater), the findings offer implications for farmed species resource management. The analysis here utilizes the output of Deliverable 3.1 Database on biomass trade, production, demand, and biodiversity proxies. For this analysis, we use a panel of 99 aquaculture producer countries during 2010-2020 and apply two-way fixed-effect regressions.

Next, we turn to Vietnam's Mekong Delta as a case study to explore the landscape-level impacts of aquaculture sustainability certification. The mangrove ecosystems in Vietnam support a wide range of biodiversity, including 521 species from fish to birds, mammals, reptiles, bivalves, sea cucumbers, insects, and plants. However, 148 species are reported to experience population declines. Between 1973 and 2020, Vietnam lost approximately 2150 hectares of mangrove annually, primarily due to aquaculture expansion. We ask whether aquaculture sustainability certification can help protect mangrove habitats. To answer this, we rely on a grid-based panel data, where each grid (cell) represents a mangrove-aquaculture landscape. We then evaluate

the impact of cells' exposure to certified shrimp farms on two mangrove outcomes: absolute mangrove area and relative share within each landscape. We establish credible counterfactuals using matching techniques that account for the geographical traits and historical land-use changes in the local and adjacent landscapes. We then quantify the average and dynamic effects of certification with two-way fixed effects and event-study analysis. This analysis draws on spatial data from Milestone MS6 Identification of aquaculture production sites.

Our findings highlight the nuanced impacts of the two studied governance measures across scales. At the country level, NTMs' impact on domestic aquaculture production is shaped by four aquaculture archetypes that represent diverse contexts of aquaculture development. Emerging aquaculture producers (mainly Central Asia and West Africa countries) benefit most from the positive impacts of NTMs. In contrast, the inherent characteristics of the other archetypes hint at systemic barriers against the implementation and compliance with NTMs, even in the short term. When compliance requires substantial fixed-cost investments, developing aquaculture producers (Southeast Asia and some Latin American countries) are most negatively affected. But when compliance involves marginal costs associated with inspections or certification, wealthy aquaculture producers (Western Europe, the U.S., Canada, and Japan) are most negatively affected. For aquaculture producers with limited aquatic food engagement (Eastern European and a few African, Latin American, and Asian countries), NTMs show consistently insignificant effects, reinforcing their categorization as having limited aquaculture growth. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating aquaculture archetypes into the designs of trade policy instruments. At the local level, aquaculture sustainability certification shows a positive association with mangrove outcomes, signaling positive news for mangrove conservation through market mechanisms. However, its minimal and localized effect suggests the need to revisit the targets of certification schemes and to complement conservation with other policies.

INTRODUCTION

Global aquaculture expansion is a key link between sea biomass and biodiversity. On one end, the global aquaculture sector heavily relies on marine capture fisheries for essential feed ingredients, such as fish meal and fish oil (Tacon & Metian, 2008). Between 2000 and 2020, aquaculture's share in global fishmeal and fish oil consumption increased significantly, now accounting for approximately 75% of fishmeal and 71% of fish oil usage (International Fishmeal and Fish Oil Organisation [IFFO], 2024). On the other end, the sector's rapid growth has also led to several environmental consequences, including the introduction of invasive species, marine and freshwater eutrophication, and the destruction of mangrove habitats (Gephart & Golden, 2022), all of which affect both aquatic and terrestrial biodiversity. Yet, aquaculture growth remains important, as this sector plays a key role in global food security and contributes to economic development across regions worldwide (FAO, 2024). That said, **is it possible to promote aquaculture expansion in a way that minimizes environmental impacts, especially on biodiversity?** Given the global scale and environmental consequences of aquaculture expansion, this deliverable focuses on two trade-related governance measures: non-tariff measures targeting import flows and sustainability standards relevant for export-oriented production.

The aquaculture sector is distributed unevenly; as of 2022, over 90% of global aquaculture production occurs in Asia, while other countries in Africa are projected to experience the fastest growth in the coming years (FAO, 2024). This expansion is closely tied to the fisheries sector. Latin America remains the world's leading producer of fishmeal, while both Latin America and Southeast Asia contribute substantially to the global fish oil supply (IFFO, 2021). Most fishmeal is imported by Asian countries for aquaculture feed, while fish oil has a broader global market, with Europe as the leading importer, followed by Asia and Latin America (IFFO, 2021). This geographic unevenness in production drives the expansion of aquatic product trade.

We first examine standard-like non-tariff measures (NTMs) at the global scale. To mitigate the environmental as well as social risks associated with the trade of aquatic food and feed, many countries have implemented NTMs, including sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures and technical barriers to trade (TBTs). These measures function as public standards, targeting a wide range of objectives from food safety, animal health, plant protection, to safeguarding global common resources (Ababouch et al., 2023). They are determined to be non-discriminatory and often seen as *'the grey zone where trade policies meet national regulations'* (UNCTAD, 2018, 2019). Despite that, they may as well be used for protectionist purposes (e.g., Pace, 2011), relating to a large body of literature focusing on their impacts on trade flows (e.g., Anders & Caswell, 2009; van Tongeren et al., 2009; Xiong & Beghin, 2014). However, there is an often-neglected aspect of NTMs – how do they impact the domestic aquaculture industries within the implementing countries? Indeed, NTMs are now implemented not only by high-income countries, such as the U.S. and the EU, but also by many lower-income countries (Ababouch et al., 2023). Complying with NTMs increases administrative hurdles and compliance costs (Jafari & Britz, 2018), which may present various challenges for these countries. In high-income countries, the extra regulations may contribute to the already elevated level of stringency, often seen as a barrier to aquaculture growth (Lasner & Gimpel, 2024; Naylor et al., 2023). In lower-income countries where technical and financial capacities are often limited (Ponte et al., 2014), enforcing NTMs may unintentionally hinder their domestic industry growth. These unintended

consequences of NTMs could further reinforce the existing geographic disparities in global aquaculture production.

We then zoom in on a more local value chain to explore the biodiversity impacts, focusing on shrimp farming and mangrove ecosystems, and examine the role of aquaculture sustainability certification. Shrimp farming alone accounted for around 25% of global fishmeal and 10% of fish oil consumption in 2006 (Tacon & Metian, 2008). This production system is also widely considered the leading cause of mangrove loss, particularly in Southeast Asia (Goldberg et al., 2020). Mangrove habitats provide unique and highly productive ecosystems that serve as crucial breeding grounds, nurseries, and complex habitats for a wide range of marine and terrestrial species (Boyd et al., 2022; Carugati et al., 2018). They also improve local ecosystem functioning and support the connectivity of coastal seascapes (Corte et al., 2021). Despite increased restoration and protection efforts, mangrove habitats continue to face threats, and the effectiveness of these efforts remains uncertain (Hagger et al., 2022).

In response, voluntary market-based mechanisms, such as third-party sustainability certification, have emerged. The major sustainability certifications, including Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), Best Aquaculture Practices [BAP], and GLOBALG.A.P., comprise environmental, social, animal welfare, and traceability requirements. Specifically, these certifications outline requirements for environmental management, including impact assessments, biodiversity conservation, and water quality monitoring, among others. Although the adoption of certification in aquaculture has expanded over the past two decades, questions remain about their actual environmental results (Bush et al., 2013; Rector et al., 2023).

The above-mentioned governance measures – standard-like NTMs and sustainability certification – represent trade-related leverage points for reducing biodiversity loss associated with sea biomass. We focus on these two governance measures to address the task T3.4 and to fill the current literature gaps. We ask two main questions:

- i) Does strengthening market standards, via the implementation of standard-like non-tariff measures, come at the cost of domestic aquaculture growth?
- ii) Can aquaculture sustainability certification help protect high conservation value (HCV) areas like mangroves?

To address these questions, we extend the conceptual framework developed in Deliverable 2.1 and outline the impact mechanisms of non-tariff measure and sustainability certification. We have integrated expert and stakeholder knowledge into our work in two key ways. Firstly, we adopt the aquaculture development archetype developed by Partelow et al. (2025) to contextualize the impacts across distinct national socio-economic, regulatory, and ecological contexts. This framework, originally developed by aquaculture scholars through cluster analysis of over 40 aquaculture-specific factors, offers an empirical basis to develop further hypotheses (see Conceptual Framework, p.10-13). Its design aligns with machine learning-based approaches for identifying determinants of aquaculture expansion. We integrate this framework as a moderating variable within our econometric models to assess how aquaculture contexts influence NTM effects on production output (see Methods, p. 17). Secondly, it is important to note that the impact mechanisms of sustainability certification were validated by stakeholders from the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), ensuring the relevance of our sampling

strategy (See Methods, p. 21). Our overall methodology combines spatial and econometric approaches, including a set of quasi-experimental analytical tools such as two-way fixed-effect regressions, matching, and event-study analysis. We utilize the country-level data described in Deliverable 3.1, supplemented by a high-resolution (30m) land-use dataset for the case study of Vietnam's Mekong Delta (see section Methods, p.15).

Overall, we aim to provide empirical insights into how sustainable aquaculture expansion can mitigate biodiversity loss from sea biomass trade. Understanding how NTMs affect aquaculture output and the factors that moderate these impacts could offer valuable insights into potential shifts in industry structure and thus domestic aquatic resource management. Furthermore, evaluating how sustainability certification impacts unfold at the landscape level can help identify effective mangrove conservation initiatives.

OBJECTIVES

This deliverable (D3.4) aims to provide empirical evidence for “Quantified ex-post biodiversity threats of trade in biomass from sea.” To achieve this, the report addresses the following objectives:

- Outline the impact pathways of the two governance measures of focus: standard-like non-tariff measures and aquaculture sustainability certification, while conceptualizing their impacts within the context of EU-related aquaculture development.
- Specify the methodology adopted for analysing each measure, including the ex-post econometric methods as well as the data collection and processing techniques.
- Estimate the impacts of non-tariff measures on aquaculture output across four key profiles of aquaculture-producing nations.
- Estimate the impacts of aquaculture sustainability certification on protecting mangroves in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam - the case study.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This section outlines the background and impact mechanism for the studied governance measures in aquatic food trade – standard-like non-tariff measures and aquaculture sustainability certification.

1. Standard-like non-tariff measures

Background

Standard-like NTMs are regulatory tools implemented by governments to align market entry requirements with domestic regulations. These regulations are collectively known as standard-like non-tariff measures (NTMs) and encompass sanitary and phytosanitary measures (SPS) and technical barriers to trade (TBT). When a country introduces a new NTM, the notification typically includes the content of the measure, the national regulations or laws it is based on, and references to relevant international standards, such as the Codex Alimentarius Commission for food safety and quality, FAO technical guidelines, the World Organisation for Animal Health, the International Plant Protection Convention for aquatic plants, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (ePing SPS & TBT Platform, n.d.). Examples of how countries implement NTMs include: the EU regulating aquaculture establishments and transporters of aquatic animals, Indonesia making several fishery commodities subject to compulsory inspection; Brazil establishing standards regarding exploiting native or exotic fish from continental, marine and estuarine waters (ePing SPS & TBT Platform, n.d.).

These measures provide consumers with confidence that the products being traded in the country are safe, sourced from sustainably managed operations, or legally processed, among other objectives (Ababouch et al., 2023). Because NTMs must be justified based on specific objectives – food safety, animal health, plant protection, protection of human and territory from pests and diseases (ePing SPS & TBT Platform, n.d.), they are inherently aligned with sustainable development goals, such as “Sustainable consumption and production” and “Life below water” (Kravchenko et al., 2019). Moreover, previous studies show that environmental provisions in trade agreements, with similar regulatory goals, can lead to improved climate performance and reduced deforestation (e.g., Abman et al., 2024).

Impact mechanism

Aquaculture development archetype

We start by introducing the aquaculture development archetypes developed by Partelow et al. (2025), which provides a framework to conceptualize how the different aquaculture contexts – economic, social, environmental, and governance factors – moderate NTM effects.

On a global scale, aquaculture industries can be categorized into four distinct archetypes based on 42 sector-specific factors (Partelow et al., 2025). These factors encompass a wide array of economic, environmental, and governance dimensions, serving as crucial determinants of aquaculture development trajectories. The resulting four archetypes are: Archetype 1 – Emerging aquaculture producers, Archetype 2 – Limited aquatic food engagement, Archetype 3 – Developing aquaculture producers, and Archetype 4 – Wealthy aquaculture producers. The

countries within these archetypes exhibit significant differences in production and trade levels, consumption patterns, income levels, environmental performance, and regulatory quality (Table 1). They also have varying levels of aquatic biodiversity, which presents an opportunity for further development of aquaculture and fisheries. At the same time, it indicates a need for enhanced conservation efforts.

Table 1: Aquaculture development archetypes of EU countries – Adapted from Partelow et al. (2025)

Archetype	Selected aquaculture-specific indicators [§]
1 – Emerging aquaculture producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Economic: low production, highest growth rate ➤ Social: lowest consumption & GDP ➤ Environmental performance: lowest ➤ Governance performance: lowest ➤ Aquatic biodiversity: primarily freshwater species, lowest average total aquatic species
2 – Limited aquatic food engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Economic: low production, restricted by natural resources endowment ➤ Social: relatively average consumption, moderately above average GDP ➤ Environmental performance: above average ➤ Governance performance: moderately high ➤ Aquatic biodiversity: encompassing all three species groups – brackish, freshwater, marine; average and below total aquatic species
3 – Developing economy aquaculture producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Economic: high total production & trade ➤ Social: high consumption, moderately above average GDP ➤ Environmental performance: below average ➤ Governance performance: moderately low ➤ Aquatic biodiversity: encompassing all three groups of brackish, freshwater, & marine species; above average total aquatic species
4 – Wealthy economy aquaculture producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Economic: high total production & trade, most technologically advanced ➤ Social: highest consumption, average or below GDP ➤ Environmental performance: highest ➤ Governance performance: highest ➤ Aquatic biodiversity: encompassing all three species groups, the most diverse marine species, and the highest total aquatic species

Note: § The indicators included here are selected for display as they represent the most relevant factors affecting how NTMs influence aquaculture production output. The ranking was based on the archetype average compared to the world average. See Partelow et al. (2025)'s study for the full archetype description.

Next, we explore the pathways through which NTMs impact aquaculture production output. Theoretically, they could influence production output by shifting the supply function, due to compliance costs, and the demand function, since NTMs may provide information about the quality of the product to consumers (Jafari & Britz, 2018). Additionally, NTMs can impact domestic production by affecting trade costs and the prices of products in the domestic market. The magnitude of these impacts is likely to vary across countries, depending on income levels, industry scale, and institutional capacity (Anders & Caswell, 2009; Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2022). The net effect depends on how supply and demand, along with trade costs, interact in response to these regulatory changes.

A shift in demand

The multiple social and environmental objectives embedded in standard-like NTMs, including SPSs and TBTs, can positively shift consumer demand (Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2022; Xiong & Beghin, 2014). To do so, these measures correct market inefficiencies caused by externalities in production, distribution, and consumption (Ababouch et al., 2023). While the specific requirements of these measures vary widely across implementing countries, the overall goal is to ensure regulated products in the market with safety and improved quality attributes.

This positive demand shift matters in the context of aquaculture products, given the cultural and economic diversity of the global consumers. For example, while aquatic food is a dietary staple in many low- and middle-income countries (Belton et al., 2020), it is often met with skepticism in other cultures due to concerns over food safety and environmental impacts (Ababouch et al., 2023). As the awareness of aquatic food consumers grows (Ababouch et al., 2023), the minimum standards on safety and quality set by NTMs can enhance consumer trust and boost demand for aquaculture products. Additionally, the magnitude of the demand shift depends on how NTM-related information is communicated to consumers and how consumers value such attributes in NTM-compliant products.

For Limited aquaculture producers (Archetype 2) and Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4), where consumers are accustomed to product labelling and regulatory information, NTMs represent the minimum requirements for products in these markets, demand therefore would not be significantly shifted for Archetypes 2 & 4. However, for Emerging (Archetype 1) and Developing aquaculture producers (Archetype 3), where consumer expectations for product quality are relatively lower, implementing NTMs, coupled with increasing urban share and income level, could create a remarkable demand shift. In summary, we hypothesize that the demand shift would **positively impact** the production output of **Archetypes 1 and 3**, while **not affecting** the production output of **Archetypes 2 and 4**.

A shift in supply

Implementing standard-like NTMs often raises production costs due to increased marginal or fixed costs (Jafari & Britz, 2018; van Tongeren et al., 2009), potentially shifting the supply curve upward. Previous studies highlight the inadequate capacities of producers in many countries to meet compliance requirements (Anders & Caswell, 2009; Shepotylo, 2016). Other studies also indicate that reducing the compliance costs of NTMs through harmonization may boost production in the affected industries (e.g., Xiong & Beghin, 2014). The supply-shifting impact of NTMs often relates to variations in income levels and degrees of industrialization across countries (Anders & Caswell, 2009; Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2022).

Presumably, domestic producers should have already adhered to domestic regulations, or at least possess the capacity to do so. However, previous studies on aquaculture development and governance have highlighted disparities in enforcement and compliance across countries (e.g., Naylor et al., 2023). In high-income countries, administrative inefficiencies and discrepancies between regulations and real-world situations often lead to increased compliance costs (Naylor et al., 2023). For instance, in Germany, high bureaucratic obligations were perceived as limiting entrepreneurship, thus hindering aquaculture expansion (Lasner & Gimpel, 2024). Over-regulation is also viewed as a barrier to growth in the U.S. aquaculture industry (Jolly et al., 2023). Norway serves as a contrasting example, where industry growth and stringent regulatory

frameworks can coexist (Naylor et al., 2023). Generally, high-income countries often benefit from advanced technologies inherited from well-established fisheries sectors, which can mitigate the impacts of additional regulations.

As Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4) exhibit high levels of total aquaculture production, the best environmental performance, and the strictest regulations, implementing NTMs may not directly impact production output since domestic producers are already compliant or benefit from economies of scale. Additionally, NTMs could indirectly affect production output by limiting imports, often seen as protectionism (e.g., Pace, 2011), potentially boosting production output. In contrast, the remaining three archetypes face greater constraints in NTM compliance due to either smaller industry scale, lower regulatory quality, or lower environmental performance, or the combination of all. We expect these three archetypes to experience a negative NTM effect on production output compared to Archetype 4. **In summary**, we hypothesize that the supply shift will **negatively impact** the production output of **Archetypes 1-3**, while **having no effect or improving** the production output of **Archetype 4**.

Trade cost effect

The trade cost effect refers to an increase in bilateral import costs, such as those incurred for certification. Although this does not directly shift the supply or demand curves, it can lead to higher domestic prices by raising the cost of imports (Jafari & Britz, 2018). In response, domestic producers may increase output, i.e., move upward along the supply curve. This trade cost mechanism is likely relevant across all archetypes, but its magnitude may vary depending on market preference and regulatory quality, among other factors. For example, markets in Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4) are more responsive to signals of aquatic food quality changes, yet the high regulatory stringency may impose higher compliance costs on importers, potentially lowering imports and incentivizing domestic production. **In summary**, we hypothesize a **positive impact of NTMs**, through trade costs, on production output **across all archetypes**.

Derived hypotheses on the net impact of NTMs across archetypes

Determining the overall NTM effect on domestic production output is complex. The net effect is the sum of the different pathways affected by mediating factors, such as industry scale, income level, environmental performance, and regulatory quality. Based on the interplay of demand and supply shifts, and trade cost effect, we hypothesize that Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4) will be least affected, or may even benefit, from implementing additional standard-like NTMs. For the other three archetypes, the direction and magnitude of the net effect are more uncertain, as the relative strength of each pathway remains unclear. We therefore hypothesize that NTMs could have either negative or positive impacts on aquaculture production of Limited, Emerging, and Developing aquaculture producers (Archetypes 1-3).

2. Aquaculture sustainability certification

Background

Aquaculture sustainability certification (henceforth, sustainability certification) emerged in response to the environmental and social challenges from the aquaculture sector's rapid expansion, which also indicates a shift from traditional state regulations (Bush et al., 2013). Several major organizations have played a role in this development: the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) established in 2010 through a collaboration between the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and the Sustainable Trade Initiative; Best Aquaculture Practices (BAP) established in 2002 by the Global Aquaculture Alliance; Friend of the Sea launched in 2006; and GLOBALG.A.P. introduced in 2004 (Bush et al., 2013; Rector et al., 2023).

Impact framework

In theory

The primary goal of sustainability certification is to encourage the best aquaculture practices, thereby increasing consumer trust and providing legitimacy to producers (Vince & Haward, 2019). To achieve this, these certification schemes include a comprehensive set of requirements: 98 indicators by ASC, 70 audit clauses by BAP, and 219 indicators by GLOBALG.A.P. (ASC, 2023; BAP, 2023; GLOBALG.A.P., 2024). In general, the schemes can be boiled down to the key themes of food safety, social accountability, environmental responsibility, animal welfare, and traceability. Compliance is ensured through audit processes and monitoring systems conducted both internally by farms and externally by independent third parties. Farms are required to conduct annual self-assessments and maintain records of production activities and environmental performance. Approved certification bodies then validate these internal assessments through on-site inspections, review of management records, and interviews with employees.

These certifications address the sea biomass impact of aquaculture via marine ingredients metrics. These include Feed Conversion, Fish in Fish out, and Forage Fish Dependency ratios, which generally mandate the efficient utilization of wild-caught fish in relation to the quantity of aquatic products and the full traceability of feed purchases and usage. Furthermore, BAP and ASC explicitly prohibit the use of ingredients originating from endangered species (ASC, 2023; BAP, 2023).

To address biodiversity impacts, sustainability certifications set various requirements on site selection, environmental management, and species conservation. For example, these requirements include avoiding siting in protected areas, natural wetlands, and critical habitats of endangered species; maintaining a minimum buffer between farms and marine environments; and allowing corridors for the movement of native wildlife (ASC, 2023). Specifically for mangrove ecosystems, no siting is allowed for farms built after May 1999, except for pumping stations and canals. For farms built or permitted before, compensation is required via rehabilitation of 50% of the affected ecosystem (ASC, 2023). GLOBAL G.A.P. requires that farms built in those areas from May 1999 to April 2008 be retired or rehabilitated within three years of certification (GLOBALG.A.P., 2024).

In practice

Adopting sustainability certification in practice presents a mix of achievements and challenges. One of the most notable benefits is the increased market access and profitability for certified farms (Dong et al., 2021). For instance, in Vietnam, ASC-certified shrimp received a premium of 2000- 5000 VND per kg (~ 0.07 – 0.17 EUR), Naturland-certified shrimp received 3000-5000 VND

per kg ($\sim 0.1 - 0.17$ EUR) (Dong et al., 2021; Watanabe & Ubukata, 2023). This economic benefit often motivates the adoption and promotion of certification by local governments and non-government organizations (Watanabe & Ubukata, 2023). Additionally, there is evidence to support the improved environmental impacts of certification. ASC-certified farms in Asia demonstrate drastically less water exchange, better energy efficiency, and better feed management compared to non-certified farms (Davis & Boyd, 2021).

Nevertheless, some limitations exist within and upon the implementation of these certification frameworks. Sustainability certifications have been criticized for primarily focusing on environmental issues at the farm level without addressing the social sustainability issues and "far-field" impacts (e.g., land-based resource use) (Rector et al., 2023). The unit of certification is typically an individual farm, which overlooks the collective impacts of multiple certified farms in a given location (Bush et al., 2013). Interestingly, the financial incentives are not always met in reality. In some cases, the price premium was insufficient to attract farmers' engagement (Watanabe & Ubukata, 2023). In other cases, the application and maintenance costs are prohibitively high for a typical rural household (Dong et al., 2021).

Derived theory of change at the landscape level

Certification serves as a leverage point for environmental stewardship. Certification may affect mangrove coverage within the spatial and contractual boundaries of certified farms (additionality) and beyond those boundaries (spillover) (see Fig. A1). Therefore, the landscape-level effect is the sum of the additionality and spillover effects induced by sustainability certification, or more precisely by exposure to certified farm(s), on mangrove cover within a single spatial unit. The additionality effect (cf. Börner et al., 2017) is bound by certification requirements at the farm level. For instance, farms converted from mangroves after 1999 are generally ineligible for certification, while certain essential infrastructure with permission or those established on mangroves before 1999 are allowed to offset their impacts by restoring an equivalent area to the lost mangroves (ASC, 2023). Mangrove cover is then expected to be maintained during the certification period and is audited annually, thereby presumably resulting in a positive direct effect. The spillover effect stems from the fact that aquaculture farms are integrated in the surrounding social-ecological systems (cf. Bush et al., 2010). Hence, the presence of one or multiple certified farms, via their own indirect behaviours and indirect influence on their peers, may exert either negative or positive effects on mangrove cover beyond the certified farms. The positive indirect effect occurs when certified farms restore mangrove outside certified areas and/or encourage neighbouring farms to adopt mangrove conservation practices for certification eligibility. At the same time, the negative indirect effects may result from certified farms displacing mangrove-clearing activities to nearby non-certified areas and/or inducing non-certified actors to do so (see further on spillover mechanisms in Börner et al., 2017). While the additionality in mangrove cover is likely positive under strong auditing and monitoring, or at worse, null; the spillovers could further enhance or diminish this additionality, leading to potentially positive or negative aggregate effects across different landscape scales.

METHODS

This section outlines the empirical design and data for analysing standard-like non-tariff measures and aquaculture sustainability certification.

1. Standard-like non-tariff measures and aquaculture production output

1.1. Empirical design

Baseline model

To analyze the impact of non-tariff measures (NTMs) on aquaculture production output, we construct the following empirical model:

$$AquaProd_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NTM_{it-1} + \beta_k Controls_{it} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_t + \epsilon_{it} , \quad (\text{Eq 1})$$

where i and t represent importing (implementing) countries and time, respectively; β_0 is the constant term; NTM_{it-1} is the count of NTMs; $Controls_{it}$ is a vector of control variables (including population, GDP per capita, applied tariff rates, and trade agreements); α_i and ε_t are year and country fixed effects (FE); ϵ_{it} represents unobserved factors. Our identification strategy compares the change in aquaculture production output of a country due to the change in the cumulative number of effective NTMs it imposes on its aquatic food market.

As the baseline, we estimate Eq (1) using two-way fixed effects models to control for potential endogeneity from omitted variables. Country FEs account for time-invariant or relatively stable factors such as natural resource availability (e.g., area of inland water, exclusive economic zone). Year FEs capture temporal macroeconomic variations, such as competitive pressures from regional and global aquaculture producers in a given year. Together, these fixed effects help mitigate the endogeneity of NTMs.

The dependent variable, a country's annual total aquaculture output ($AquaProd_{it}$), is a sum of output volume of all production systems existing in the respective country (i.e., freshwater, marine, brackish). We measure production output in volume rather than value to avoid distortion from certain aquatic species, being export-oriented and more highly priced, which could disproportionately influence the total value and misrepresent the country's overall production status quo.

The key explanatory variables (NTM_{it-1}) represent the cumulative numbers of standard-like non-tariff measures regulating aquatic food markets, specifically products under the Harmonized System's code HS03 "Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates". We employ three specifications: (1) the cumulative numbers of SPS and TBT measures combined (NTM), (2) only SPS measures (SPS), and (3) only TBT measures (TBT) and conduct separate regressions for each. This approach allows us to assess the consistency of the effect of standard-like NTMs and simultaneously consider potential differences in the effects of SPS and TBT measures. It is worth re-emphasizing that these NTM variables reflect the measures

a country adopts and implements domestically to regulate the import trade of aquatic food products¹.

We use one-year lagged values of standard-like NTMs, NTM_{it-1} , to address potential reverse causality. Reverse causality might exist between production output and the implementation of NTMs, akin to the relationship between trade flow and trade policy measures (Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2022). This implies that the production level may justify the imposition of standard-like NTMs, and these measures may influence the production level. For instance, certain developing countries with export-oriented industries may leverage new standards to enhance their competitive advantage and increase market share in trade (Anders & Caswell, 2009). NTMs could also emerge due to governmental support for declining industries (Disdier & Tongeren, 2010). Another reason for using NTM_{it-1} is that production volume would not instantaneously adjust to changes in regulations within a single year. For instance, production cycles vary between 3-12 months depending on the fish species (Kestemont, 1995; Wing-Keong & Nicholas, 2013). Similarly, complete compliance with HACCP standards could take anywhere from two months to five years for fish processors in Brazil (Donovan et al., 2001).

Heterogeneity analysis

To investigate the moderating role of the four archetypes, we include the interaction terms between NTM variables and archetype dummies (Eq 2):

$$AquaProd_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NTM_{it-1} + \beta_2 NTM_{it-1} * Archetype1 + \beta_3 NTM_{it-1} * Archetype2 + \beta_4 NTM_{it-1} * Archetype3 + Control_{it}\beta_k + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_t + \epsilon_{it}, \text{ (Eq 2)}$$

Here, Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4) is the reference category, with β_1 being the estimate of NTM effect on Archetype 4. Coefficients β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 respectively indicate the differences of NTM effect on the production output of Archetypes 1, 2, 3 (Emerging, Limited, and Developing aquaculture producers) compared to Archetype 4. According to our Conceptual framework, the corresponding hypotheses are: H1: $\beta_1 \geq 0$ (NTMs have a non-negative impact on Wealthy aquaculture producers); H2: $\beta_2 < 0$ (Emerging aquaculture producers experience a weaker or negative NTM effect); H3: $\beta_3 < 0$ (Limited aquaculture producers experience a weaker or negative NTM effect), and H4: $\beta_4 < 0$ (Developing aquaculture producers experience a weaker or negative NTM effect). We estimate Eq (2) using two-way fixed effect models.

Using Archetype 4 – Wealthy aquaculture producers as the reference category, we can derive the NTM effects on Archetype 4 countries and the differences in effects for the other archetypes relative to Archetype 4. To enable direct comparison across all archetypes, we repeat the moderation regressions using each of the other archetypes as the reference category.

1.2. Country-level data

Table 2 summarizes the key variables used for this analysis, which are sourced from multiple databases. Data on the dependent variable - aquaculture production output - comes from the

¹ We acknowledge that NTMs imposed by a country's trade partners or the rest of the world could also influence its aquaculture production output. We however exclude them from our models because: First, they are significantly and positively correlated with the domestic NTMs, leading to multicollinearity issues. Second, the total count of external NTMs is large and, as a sum, shows no meaningful marginal changes yearly. We argue that the year fixed effects considered in our regression specification already capture the aggregate effect of such external measures.

FishSTAT Database (FAO, 2022), which reports production volume (in ton of live weights) for various species across production systems in over 200 countries from 1950 to 2020. We measure the dependent variable as the total annual production volumes of freshwater, brackish water, and marine aquaculture. The key explanatory variables - the cumulative counts of effective standard-like NTMs, SPS and TBT measures - are extracted from the UNCTAD NTM TRAINS database (WITS, 2022). We focus on measures imposed on aquatic food products under categories A and B of the Harmonized System's code HS03 "Fish and crustaceans, molluscs and other aquatic invertebrates". Other control variables are derived from MACMAP, WTO Stats, and the World Development Indicators (WDI) databases (ITC, 2023; WTO, 2023; WB, 2022). We aggregate these data to the country-year level.

To ensure comprehensive and reliable data coverage, we select 2010 as the starting year of our analysis². We focus on 99 countries, out of the 213 countries documented in the FishSTAT database, including those with the most complete information across variables. To maximize country inclusion, we impute missing data for a few countries with only minor gaps in observations³. Countries excluded from our sample largely lack consistent information on tariff and non-tariff measures. The final dataset yields a balanced panel of 1089 observations (99 countries x 11 years, 2010-2020).

This sample includes 25 Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1), 28 Limited aquaculture producers (Archetype 2), 25 Developing aquaculture producers (Archetype 3), and 19 Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4). Archetype 1 countries include Armenia, Benin, Bolivia, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Lao PDR, Liberia, Mozambique, Nepal, Niger, Pakistan, Papua New Guinea, Paraguay, Rwanda, Senegal, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, and Zimbabwe. Archetype 2 countries include Austria, Belgium, Brunei Darussalam, Bulgaria, Costa Rica, Cyprus, Czechia, El Salvador, Estonia, Georgia, Guyana, Hungary, Iceland, Israel, Jordan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mauritius, Poland, Qatar, Singapore, Slovakia, Slovenia, Suriname, Switzerland, Trinidad and Tobago, United Arab Emirates, and Uruguay. Archetype 3 countries include Argentina, Bangladesh, Brazil, Cambodia, China, Colombia, Ecuador, Egypt, Guatemala, Honduras, Indonesia, Malaysia, Mexico, Morocco, Myanmar, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Russian Federation, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Thailand, Turkey, and Vietnam. Archetype 4 countries include Chile, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Portugal, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, and the U.S. See Partelow et al. (2025)'s study for full list of countries.

We apply the inverse hyperbolic sine (i.e., arcsinh) transformation⁴ to most variables, except for the MFN tariff rate, which is transformed using the $\ln(1 + \text{MFN})$ transformation, a common practice in trade policy analysis. The main reason for the transformations is the skewed distribution of variables. Since both the dependent variable and the primary explanatory

² The first round of data collection started around 2010 and covers 109 countries as of 2019 (UNCTAD 2018).

³ For a few countries (e.g., Armenia, Bangladesh, Liberia, Nepal, Peru, Suriname), which have missing data on tariff and NTM for a single year, we impute the missing data with data from the next year available. This procedure was conducted using R tidy package's function *fill*, with the direction set to 'downup'.

⁴ $\text{arcsinh}(x) = \ln(x + \sqrt{x^2 + 1})$

variables are specified as arcsinh, the estimated impacts of NTMs on $AquaProd_{it}$ are interpreted as semi-elasticities.

Table 2. Definitions of key variables

Variable	Definition	Source
$AquaProd_{it}$	Total aquaculture production quantity by country in in year t; measured in tons of live weight and arcsinh transformed	FishSTAT (FAO, 2022)
NTM_{it-1}	Cumulative number of Sanitary & Phytosanitary (SPS) and Technical barriers to trade (TBT) measures country i imposed in year t-1 for product group HS03 “Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates”; measure in count & transformed as arcsinh	TRAINS (WITS, 2022)
SPS_{it-1}	Cumulative number of Sanitary & Phytosanitary (SPS) measures country i imposed in year t-1 for product group HS03 “Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates”; measure in count & transformed as arcsinh	TRAINS (WITS, 2022)
TBT_{it-1}	Cumulative number of Technical barriers to trade (TBT) measures country i imposed in year t-1 for product group HS03 “Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates”; measure in count & transformed as arcsinh	TRAINS (WITS, 2022)
Pop_{it}	Total population of country in in year t. Measured originally as person, transformed as arcsinh.	WDI (WB, 2022)
$GDPpcap_{it-1}$	Per capita values for GDP in current international dollars converted by purchasing power parity conversion factor of country i in in year t-1. Measured originally as “current \$”, transformed as arcsinh.	WDI (WB, 2022)
TA_{it}	Cumulative number of effective trade agreements country i associated with in year t. Measured as count, transformed as arcsinh.	WDI (WB, 2022)
MFN_{it-1}	Most-favoured nation (MFN) tariff rate (simple average with ad valorem equivalents %) that country i applied in year t-1 for product group HS03. Measured originally as “percent” & transformed as log for tariff rate plus one i.e., $\ln(1 + \text{tariff})$.	WTO Stats (WTO, 2023)

2. Aquaculture sustainability certification and mangrove cover

2.1. Study area

Vietnam is selected as our case study for its significant role in global aquatic food production and trade, as well as its ecological importance. The country exports seafood to over 160 markets worldwide, with its top four export destinations being the U.S., the EU, Japan, and China (IFFO, 2021). In 2020, Vietnam imported approximately 200,000 tons of fishmeal, making it one of the largest fishmeal importers in Asia (IFFO, 2021). Fish oil, another critical input in aquaculture – particularly shrimp feed – is also heavily imported. Vietnam imported 17,000 tons of fish oil, primarily from Chile and Norway.

Since the early 1990s, shrimp farming has been a major driver of conflicts with mangrove ecosystems. The Vietnamese government encouraged aquaculture expansion through policies such as Decision 347-CT, which allowed for the conversion of land into shrimp ponds (Watanabe & Ubukata, 2023). Simultaneously, the government issued zoning regulations promoting

mangrove reforestation, requiring aquaculture operations to maintain a minimum of 60% mangrove cover within their facility areas (Watanabe & Ubukata, 2023).

This study focuses on the Mekong Delta region – Vietnam’s most critical area for aquaculture and mangrove conservation. The Mekong Delta (Lat. 8°5’N–9°5’N, Long. 103°5’E–107°0’E) contains 84% of the country’s total mangrove area (T. H. Pham et al., 2022). These mangroves include 98 known species, typically found along narrow coastlines (T. H. Pham et al., 2022; Truong & Do, 2018). The 14 provinces in the Mekong Delta contribute 70% of Vietnam’s total aquaculture farming area and account for 52% of its annual aquaculture output (Truong & Do, 2018). Notably, more than 70% of Vietnam’s shrimp production is exported to international markets (Dong et al., 2021).

From 1973 to 2020, Vietnam lost an average of 2150 hectares of mangrove each year due to aquaculture expansion (T. H. Pham et al., 2022). While most mangrove areas continue to face high deforestation pressure, some communes have experienced promising trends. Between 2015 and 2020, these areas achieved an annual mangrove gain of 2.8% driven by restoration efforts from the government and non-governmental organizations (T. H. Pham et al., 2022). As of 2020, Vietnam’s total mangrove area is estimated at 188,000 hectares, 8% of which is identified as restorable (Ocean Wealth, n.d.).

Mangrove ecosystems in Vietnam support a rich array of biodiversity. Mangrove-affiliated biodiversity encompasses species classified as having suitable habitat in IUCN habitat categories “1.7 Forest - Subtropical/Tropical Mangrove Vegetation Above High Tide Level” and “12.7 Marine Intertidal - Mangrove Submerged Roots” (Sievers et al., 2023). Accordingly, the mangrove-affiliated biodiversity in Vietnam comprises 521 species, including 66 from the Plantae kingdom and 455 from the Animalia kingdom (Table 3). They mainly include ray-finned fish, birds, mammals, reptiles, cartilaginous fish, gastropods, as well as some amphibians, bivalves, cephalopods, sea cucumbers, insects, and plants. Although the majority are classified as Least Concern (439 species), several species require increased conservation attention: 9 species are Critically Endangered, 15 Endangered, 22 Vulnerable, and 16 Near Threatened (Table 3). Furthermore, population declines have been recorded for 148 species.

Table 3: Mangrove-affiliated biodiversity in Vietnam and their IUCN Red List categories

	Critically endangered	Endangered	Vulnerable	Near threatened	Least concern	Data deficient & NA	Total
Plant	0	0	1	3	57	5	66
Animal	9	15	21	13	354	43	455
Ray-finned fish	0	0	5	1	149	32	187
Amphibians	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Birds	1	0	5	9	143	0	158
Bivalves	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Cephalopods	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
Cartilaginous fish	3	6	1	0	1	4	15
Gastropods	0	0	0	0	11	2	13

	Critically endangered	Endangered	Vulnerable	Near threatened	Least concern	Data deficient & NA	Total
Sea cucumbers	0	1	0	0	0	1	2
Insects	0	0	0	0	4	0	4
Mammals	2	6	8	2	22	0	40
Reptiles	3	2	2	1	20	3	31

Note: The classes under Plant include Liliopsida, Magnoliopsida, and Polypodiopsida. Source: IUCN, 2022.

2.2. Empirical design

Treatment

We use data of aquaculture farms certified by the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) standard as a proxy for sustainability certification, our treatment variable, for three main reasons. First, ASC is one of the leading certification bodies in global aquaculture (Davis & Boyd, 2021). ASC-certified products are sourced from over 190 countries and distributed across 126 markets, with the EU representing the largest consumption region, accounting for 26,022 of the total 29,768 products (ASC, 2025). Second, ASC plays a prominent role in Vietnam’s certified aquaculture sector. One third of all certified aquaculture farms in Vietnam are accredited by ASC (Dong et al., 2021). By 2025, Vietnam has the highest number of ASC-certified farm sites (total 594) and ranks fourth in terms of certified seafood production volume, with an annual output of 275,000 metric tons (ASC, 2025). Lastly, ASC provides the most transparent and accessible data among major certification bodies. It offers detailed, publicly available audit reports, enabling robust spatial analysis. In comparison, other certification schemes either have limited presence in Vietnam or lack publicly available data. This data availability enables us to build a spatially explicit dataset for farm sites that have applied and received ASC certification between 2012 and 2020.

Design of analysis unit & counterfactuals

We create our samples via four main steps. First, we aggregate the original 30-meter land-use and land-cover (LULC) pixels with four factors of 10, 20, 30, and 50. The unit of analysis is subsequently equivalent to an area of 9-, 36-, 81-, and 225-hectare (ha) area – hereafter referred to as ‘cell’. This selection of aggregation factors serves as a starting point for our spatial analysis and is not based on any specific administrative or ecological unit. In the Mekong Delta, shrimp farms range in size from 0.5 to 2 ha, although there are also larger farms with varying sizes up to 15 ha (Joffre et al., 2015; Lan, 2013). Therefore, the 9-ha landscapes may contain 3-18 aquaculture farms or even just one large-scale farm, whereas the 225-ha landscapes may include around 15-112 farms.

Second, we apply a set of filtering conditions to these cells. We only consider cells that contain both aquaculture land use and mangrove land cover at any time between 1990-2020, constituting mangrove-aquaculture landscapes. All sample cells must also be located within the boundaries of the Mekong Delta provinces. To identify potentially illegal aquaculture expansion sites, we overlay the sample cells onto polygons of marine protected areas (retrieved from UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2024); we detect no overlap between these two layers, indicating the absence of illegal aquaculture sites in our study area. To control for the exposure of the sample cells to marine protected areas, we include a matching covariate measuring the distance from

each cell to the nearest protected area (see below). Additionally, to more accurately quantify the effects of sustainability certification on mangrove outcomes separate from other local conservation efforts, we exclude cells located within cultural and historical sites, national parks, Ramsar sites, and nature reserves. We also account for potential spillover effects from these protected sites by including the shortest distance from each cell to these types as matching covariates in our matching strategy (see below).

Third, we categorize cells into treated and control cells. A treated cell is therefore defined as one that has been exposed to certified aquaculture farms, while its counterfactual (control cell) shares comparable geographic and administrative characteristics and historical land use trends but has never been exposed to any certified farms. This is done by overlaying certified farm polygons with cell rasters and counting the number of polygons intersecting each cell⁵. We repeat this step for four spatial scales.

Fourth, we identify a set of credible counterfactuals that reflect the criteria of historical land use and closely match the geographical characteristics of the treated cells for four spatial scales respectively. To do this, we apply propensity-score matching with a calliper of 0.25, a one-to-five ratio (treated-control), nearest neighbor, and without replacement. The propensity score estimates the probability for a cell to be treated as a function of three groups of matching covariates: i) geographical and administrative attributes of cells, ii) historical LULC within each cell, and iii) the historical LULC of neighboring cells. The geographical and administrative attributes (first group) reflect the biophysical, regulatory, and value chain contexts of cells, as well as ASC's criteria for certification eligibility (see Conceptual framework). These attributes include: distance to roads; distance to coastlines, distance to MPAs and five types of other effective area-based conservation measures (biosphere, nature reserve, national parks, Ramsar sites, cultural & historical areas). They are measured by the nearest distance to cell's centroid in meters. We also include average elevation (measured in meters) and provisional and communal type attributes. Provincial associations are dummies indicating the province cell is located. Commune type indicates whether a cell is located inside a commune or ward jurisdiction, with the latter denoting a more centralized administrative level. The historical LULC of cells and the neighbouring cells (second and third groups) capture the LULC changes in each landscape (i.e., cell) and their surroundings (i.e., neighbouring cells) within two pre-certification periods, 1990-1999 and 2000-2009. The historical land-use covariates focus on seven LULC categories, including mangrove, aquaculture, rice, other crops, urban, water, and wetland, and the composition of all existing LULC. The land use mean area and annual change rate within each period are time-invariant variables calculated for each cell and period per cell. We then calculate the spatially lagged values of these variables to capture the spatial dependency of cells on their neighboring cells. Furthermore, we also construct alternative samples of matched cells without spatially biased controls by excluding control cells that are direct neighbours of treated cells to

⁵ We first determine cell farm size. For farm sites with missing data, we substitute with the minimum farm size for the respective species (shrimp) and certificate type (e.g., single site, multiple site). For instance, the minimum size for a certified single-site shrimp farm is 2,355 m², and all farm sites in these categories without a recorded size adopt this value of 2,355 m². Secondly, we generate polygons that buffer around each farm's coordinates, determined by the farm size radius. Lastly, we overlay the certified farm polygons with the cell rasters and count how many polygons intersect each cell. Cells that ever intersect any certified farm polygons are treated cells. Control cells are cells that never intersect any certified farm polygons and contain both mangrove and aquaculture land use categories any point in time between 1990 and 2020.

account for potential spatial contamination. This approach aims to generate cleaner and more genuine counterfactuals by ruling out the spill-over effect of certified cells on nearby control cells. Table 4 presents further details of these matching covariates.

Difference-in-difference estimator

We aim to quantify the average and dynamic impacts of certification on mangrove outcomes in the treated cells. To obtain the average treatment effect, we use two-way fixed-effect (TWFE) regression. This approach enables us to compare the mangrove outcome between treated cells and control cells over time:

$$Mangrove_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SC_{it} + \alpha_i + \gamma_t + \beta_3 Prov_i \gamma_t + \mathbf{Z}_{it} \beta_4 + \varepsilon_{it}, \mathbf{Eq (3)}$$

where i and t refer to cell and year. $Mangrove_{it}$ is the mangrove outcomes in cell i in year t (in hectares or percentage), SC_{it} equals the cumulative number of certified aquaculture farms in cell i in year t . α_i and γ_t represent cell and year fixed effects, respectively. We account for the time-variant changes at the province level via $Prov_i \gamma_t$. \mathbf{Z}_{it} is a set of control variables, including four land-use types: rice, crop, urban, and other relevant land-use categories. ε_{it} is the error term, we cluster standard errors at the cell level. Additionally, we repeat this regression with a binary treatment variable where SC_{it} equals to one if cell i contains at least one certified aquaculture farm in year t or zero otherwise.

To obtain the dynamic treatment effects, we employ Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille (2024)'s difference-in-differences estimator. This estimator is robust to heterogeneous treatment effects across groups and times, and especially to situations where some units might switch into or out of treatment (e.g., when certifications get expired or cancelled). To illustrate the dynamic effects of certification, an equation is specified as follows:

$$Mangrove_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_k^7 \beta_k Cert_{it+k} + \alpha_i + \gamma_t + \beta_3 Prov_i \gamma_t + \mathbf{Z}_{it} \beta_4 + \varepsilon_{it}, \mathbf{Eq (4)}$$

where $Cert_{it+k}$ are the dummy variables for k years before and after the first year cell i is exposed to sustainability certification (certification onset). A negative number represents k years before certification onset, and a positive number represents k years after that. Therefore, β_k capture the difference in mangrove cover between the treated and control cells in k years before and after certification onset.

2.3. Spatial data

We compile four balanced panel dataset including 59,427 cells of 9 ha, 16,843 cells of 36 ha, 8,053 cells of 81 ha, and 3,161 cells of 225 ha for the period of 1990-2020. Table 4 presents the definitions and sources of the treatment, outcome, and covariate variables. The treatment variables – presence and count of certified aquaculture farms – are obtained from the list of units of certification (farm sites) from ASC Website (ASC, n.d.). The outcome variables – mangrove area and share – are calculated based on the level-2 Vietnam-wide 30-year annual land use-land cover maps (Japan Aerospace Agency, Earth Observation Research Center [JAXA EORC], 2021). As these maps contain 18 different land-use and land-cover categories, we also

use them to calculate the historical land-use change for each cell. The data sources for covariates include Hijmans (2015); Massicotte and South (2025); Humanitarian Data Exchange (2023); Open Development Mekong; UNEP-WCMC and IUCN (2024).

Table 4. Definitions of key variables

Variable	Definition	Source
Outcome		
<i>Mangrove_ha_{it}</i>	Hectares; calculated by multiplying the number of mangrove pixels inside each aggregated cell by 30 m x 30 m x 0.0001	JAXA (2021) EORC
<i>Mangrove_perc_{it}</i>	Percentage (%); calculated by dividing the number of mangrove pixels by the total number of non-NA pixels inside each aggregated cell	JAXA (2021) EORC
Treatment		
<i>SC_bi_{it}</i>	Binary; 1 if any certified shrimp farm is located in cell <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> , and 0 otherwise	ASC (n.d.)
<i>SC_cont_{it}</i>	Count; the number of certified shrimp farms in cell <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	ASC (n.d.)
<i>First_cert_i</i>	The year that cell <i>i</i> first had any certified shrimp farm	ASC (n.d.)
Control Z_{it}		
<i>Rice_{it}</i>	Hectares; calculated by multiplying the number of pixels categorized as rice paddy inside each aggregated cell by 30 m x 30 m x 0.0001	JAXA (2021) EORC
<i>Crop_{it}</i>	Hectares; calculated by multiplying the number of pixels categorized as woody, other croplands, and in-house crops inside each aggregated cell by 30 m x 30 m x 0.0001	JAXA (2021) EORC
<i>Urban_{it}</i>	Hectares; calculated by multiplying the number of pixels categorized as residence high- and low-developed inside each aggregated cell by 30 m x 30 m x 0.0001	JAXA (2021) EORC
<i>Others_{it}</i>	Hectares; calculated by multiplying the number of pixels categorized as grassland, barren land, scrub, and plantation trees inside each aggregated cell by 30 m x 30 m x 0.0001	JAXA (2021) EORC
Matching covariates		
<i>Prov_i</i>	Dummies indicating whether cell <i>i</i> is located in Bac Lieu, Ben Tre, Ca Mau, Kien Giang, Long An, Soc Trang, Tien Giang, or Tra Vinh province	Humanitarian Data Exchange (2023)
<i>Commune_i</i>	Dummies indicating whether cell <i>i</i> is located in a commune, towlet, or ward	Hijmans (2015)
<i>Dist_Coast_i</i>	Meter; distance between cell <i>i</i> and the nearest coastline	Massicotte and South (2025)
<i>Dist_Road_i</i>	Meter; distance between cell <i>i</i> and the nearest road	Open Development Mekong (2016b)

Variable	Definition	Source
$Elevation_i$	Meter; the average elevation of cell i	Open Development Mekong (2016a)
$Dist_{protectarea_i}$	Includes six variables measuring the shortest distance to six different types of protected areas: marine protected areas, cultural & historical sites, national parks, nature reserves, and Ramsar sites	UNEP-WCMC and IUCN (2024)
$LU_area_mean_period_i$	The mean area (and proportion over cell area) of seven land use categories – aquaculture, rice, crop, mangrove, water, wetland, and others – in two pre-treatment periods 1990-1999 and 2000-2009	JAXA EORC (2021)
$LU_area_trend_period_i$	The change rate of area (and proportion over cell area) of seven land use categories – aquaculture, rice, crop, mangrove, water, wetland, and others – in two pre-treatment periods 1990-1999 and 2000-2009	JAXA EORC (2021)
$Neigh_LU_area_mean_period_i$	The spatial lagged mean area (and proportion over cell area) of seven land use categories – aquaculture, rice, crop, mangrove, water, wetland, and others – in two pre-treatment periods 1990-1999 and 2000-2009	JAXA EORC (2021)
$Neigh_LU_area_trend_period_i$	The spatial lagged change rate of area (and proportion over cell area) of seven land use categories – aquaculture, rice, crop, mangrove, water, wetland, and others – in two pre-treatment periods 1990-1999 and 2000-2009	JAXA EORC (2021)

The matching process aims to balance covariates between treated and control groups by achieving a standardized mean difference < 0.25 , indicating sufficiently low bias and thus a valid counterfactual. All resulted matched samples demonstrate strong matching quality, with standardized mean difference values below 0.1, variable ratio values close to 1, and standard pair difference below 0.1 (Table 5). Applying a caliper led to some treated cells and a large number of control cells being excluded. As a result, the spatially matched samples (with direct neighbors) consist of 4,535 9-ha cells, 1,774 36-ha cells, 1,055 81-ha cells, and 512 225-ha cells.

Table 5. Sample matching results

Spatial scale – Sampling technique	Sample Size (T – Treated; C – Control)	Standardized Mean Difference	Variable Ratio	Standard Pair Distance
9 ha				
0 – Unmatched	837 T + 58,635 C	0.7539	12.8593	-
1 – Standard matching	823 T + 3,918 C	0.0018	1.0078	0.0025
2 – Spatial matching with direct neighbors	803 T + 3,732 C	0.0022	1.0102	0.0025
3 – Spatial matching without direct neighbors	794 T + 3,649 C	0.0029	1.0144	0.0028
36 ha				
0 – Unmatched	353 T + 16,490 C	0.9076	7.4081	-
1 – Standard matching	346 T + 1,625 C	0.0055	1.0230	0.0071

Spatial scale – Sampling technique	Sample Size (T – Treated; C – Control)	Standardized Mean Difference	Variable Ratio	Standard Pair Distance
2 – Spatial matching with direct neighbors	342 T + 1,432 C	0.0090	1.0226	0.0095
3 – Spatial matching without direct neighbors	329 T + 1,274 C	0.0075	1.10153	0.0078
81 ha				
0 – Unmatched	230 T + 7,823 C	0.9048	7.4703	-
1 – Standard matching	224 T + 983 C	0.0086	1.0344	0.0100
2 – Spatial matching with direct neighbors	216 T + 839 C	0.0099	1.0255	0.0095
3 – Spatial matching without direct neighbors	196 T + 696 C	0.0111	1.0321	0.0115
225 ha				
0 – Unmatched	132 T + 3,029 C	1.1501	4.7037	-
1 – Standard matching	129 T + 481 C	0.0160	1.0249	0.0211
2 – Spatial matching with direct neighbors	118 T + 394 C	0.0206	1.0443	0.0220
3 – Spatial matching without direct neighbors	94 T + 254 C	0.0320	1.0712	0.0270

Note: Standardized mean difference and variable ratio of propensity scores. List of covariates used for (1) standard matching: $Prov_i$, $Commune_i$, $Prov_i$, $Dist_Coast_i$, $Elevation_i$, $Dist_protectarea_i$, $LU_area_mean_period_i$, $LU_area_trend_period_i$; (2) spatial matching with and without direct neighbors: variables in (1) + $Lag_LU_area_mean_period_i$, $Lag_LU_area_trend_period_i$. All matching models employ 5:1 nearest-neighbor matching without replacement, measured by the propensity score with a calliper of 0.25, estimated using probit regression.

Fig. 1 illustrates the overall distribution and a close-up view of the treated 9-ha cells and their matched control cells across mangrove habitats in seven Mekong Delta provinces. These sample cells are located on the west and east coasts, respectively characterized as estuary and delta mangrove types (Ocean Wealth, n.d.).

Fig. 1. Maps of the study area

Note: A) Distribution of treated and matched control 9-ha cells across the Mekong Delta. Mangrove habitats are cells that contain mangroves at least once before 1999. Treated cells are aquaculture-mangrove landscapes with at least one ASC-certified farm between 2014-2020. Control cells result from spatial matching by the geographical and administrative attributes and historical land use and land cover of themselves and their neighboring cells. B) Location of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. C) A close-up view of randomly selected treated and control 9-ha cells.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

1. Impact of standard-like non-tariff measures on aquaculture production output

1.1. Descriptive statistics

The aquaculture production landscape varies significantly across archetypes between 2010 and 2020. We observe a consistent upward trend over time, with average aquaculture production volume increasing as follows: from 15.7 to 27.3 thousand tons in Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1), from 5.4 to 8.0 thousand tons in Limited aquaculture producers (Archetype 2), from 2628.0 to 4092.8 thousand tons in Developing aquaculture producers (Archetype 3), and from 318.0 to 423.5 thousand tons in Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4). The average annual growth rate is highest for Emerging producers (Archetype 1), with an average of 14.1% per annum, followed by Developing (Archetype 3) (5.7%), Limited (Archetype 2) (5.6%), and Wealthy (Archetype 4) aquaculture producers (1.6%).

Over the years, the use of NTMs has surged across all archetypes. This is no longer a trade policy measure used only by developed countries (Archetype 2 Limited and Archetype 4 Wealthy) or the leading aquaculture producers (Archetype 3 Developing and Archetype 4 Wealthy), NTMs have proliferated in the Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1). Archetype 1 producers in fact show the highest average annual growth rate of NTM implementation (6.6%), followed by Developing producers (Archetype 3) (5.4%), Wealthy producers (Archetype 4) (5.2%), and Limited producers (Archetype 2) (4.2%) (Fig. 2A). We observe similar upward trends of SPS implementation across archetypes (Fig. 2B). However, TBT show a different pattern, with Developing producers (Archetype 3) showing the highest annual growth rate of 7% (Fig. 2C).

Fig. 2. Trend of standard-like NTM implementation across archetypes between 2010-2020: A) overall NTMs, B) Sanitary and Phyto-sanitary (SPS), C) Technical barriers to trade (TBT) measures

Note: Mean count and standard error bars of annual cumulative number of overall NTMs, SPS, and TBT measures (arcsinh-transformed) by archetype.

Fig. 3 provides a quick glance into the bivariate relationships between aquaculture production output and the cumulative number of effective overall NTMs, in general (Fig. 3A) and by archetype (Fig. 3B). It shows that the pattern of bivariate relationship is more pronounced when taking into account aquaculture archetypes. Specifically, while the first three archetypes Emerging, Limited, and Developing aquaculture producers show an upward trend of production output upon higher level of NTMs implementation, Archetype 4 – Wealthy aquaculture producers exhibit a downward trend.

Fig. 3. Scatterplot of aquaculture production output and standard-like NTMs: A) pooled sample, B) by archetype

Note: This plot uses arcsinh-transformed values of $AquaProd_{it}$ (y-axis) and NTM_{it-1} (x-axis).

1.2. The impacts of NTMs on production output by aquaculture archetypes

We first present the average effects of stand-like NTMs on aquaculture production output from two-way fixed effects regressions (Table 6). We find that imposing NTMs, especially SPS, has a positive effect on aquaculture production output over the period 2010-2020. A 1% increase in the number of NTMs is associated with a 0.16% rise in production output (90% CI: 0.01% – 0.30%), or 0.17% with SPSs (90% CI: 0.03% – 0.32%). Both coefficients are statistically significant at the 10% level. Despite this statistical significance, the semi-elasticity of aquaculture production output with respect to the imposition of NTMs (or SPSs) is relatively small (below 1). Conversely, the effect of TBT measures is negative and statistically insignificant; with a 1% increase in TBT measures linked to a 0.02% reduction in production output (90% CI: -0.13% – 0.09%).

The effects of NTMs on aquaculture production output are relatively small. This finding aligns with previous studies on NTM impact on agro-food trade flows (e.g., Santeramo & Lamonaca,

2022) and studies examining the role of governance in shaping aquaculture output (e.g., Nadarajah & Flaaten, 2017). This suggests that while governance is an influential force in aquaculture development, it cannot (yet) outweigh the dominant roles of domestic market forces.

SPS and TBT measures exhibit contrasting impacts on aquaculture production output. SPSs tend to increase aquaculture production output, while TBTs decrease it. The differing natures of these two types (mentioned in Shepotylo, 2016; van Tongeren et al., 2009) help explain this finding. SPSs are typically associated with variable costs, such as acquiring tests, certificates, or labelling. These measures offer additional product information, which aims to build consumer trust and can boost demand. In contrast, TBTs often involve substantial investments in upgrading facilities or adopting new technologies. While these investments may directly and more effectively address environmental concerns, they can be burdensome for many aquaculture producers, especially the small-holding or entrepreneurial aquaculture farmers, and do not necessarily lead to immediate consumer trust. Notably, the negative impact of TBTs is economically negligible and statistically insignificant, indicating that TBTs, though demanding, do not substantially disrupt production in the aquaculture sector.

Table 6. Impact of standard-like NTMs (overall and by type) on total aquaculture production output (OLS fixed-effect estimation) – Baseline models

	DV: <i>AquaProd_{it}</i>		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
	NTM (t-1)	SPS (t-1)	TBT (t-1)
NTM effect	0.16*	0.17*	-0.02
	(0.09)	(0.09)	(0.06)
<i>Control variables</i>			
<i>MFN_{it}</i>	3.36**	3.36**	3.22**
	(1.48)	(1.47)	(1.54)
<i>TA_{it}</i>	-0.44	-0.43	-0.42
	(0.31)	(0.31)	(0.32)
<i>Pop_{it}</i>	2.73**	2.75**	2.71**
	(0.89)	(0.88)	(0.88)
<i>GDPpcap_{it}</i>	0.66	0.65	0.73
	(0.47)	(0.48)	(0.46)
Intercept	-42.59	-42.95	-42.36
Number of observations	1089	1089	1089
Year FE (T = 11)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE (N = 99)	Yes	Yes	Yes
R2 within	0.36	0.37	0.36
R2 overall	0.50	0.49	0.48

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Next, we investigate the role of archetypes in moderating how NTMs impact aquaculture production output (Fig. 4). The output impacts of NTM on Archetype 1 – Emerging countries consistently show a positive sign, and Archetype 1 appears to add higher gains in production output from imposing NTMs than the other archetypes. For example, when countries impose SPS measures, Archetype 4 – Wealthy countries would experience a slight reduction in production output (-0.07%), while the outcome for Archetype 1 – Emerging countries would be

significantly higher by 0.41%. Using TBT measures, Archetype 3 – Developing countries would see a statistically significant reduction of 0.20%, while Archetype 1 – Emerging countries would have a 0.35% gain in comparison.

SPSs, on average, have a positive impact on production in Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1) but a negative impact in Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4). The significant and positive impact of SPSs on Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1) likely reflects the rapid expansion of intraregional trade in Africa (Gephart et al., 2024), which might have leveraged the more pronounced positive effects of high SPSs intensity (compared to lower intensities) (Santeramo & Lamonaca, 2022). Although the negative outcome in Archetype 4 is trivial and statistically insignificant, and not confirmatory of our hypotheses, it is not necessarily counterintuitive. The conventional assumption is that producers, already subject to stringent regulations, would be less likely to be affected by the implementation of new NTMs due to their capacity for compliance with minimal costs (e.g., Xiong & Beghin, 2014). However, if new NTMs come with prohibitively high compliance costs or procedural burdens for the producers within the implementing countries, the associated increased domestic demand is more easily achieved with imports than expanding domestic production. Indeed, within Archetype 4 countries, the regulatory stringency is exceptionally high (Abate et al., 2016). We observe in our data that the average level of SPSs implemented by Archetype 4 is 5.19, compared to 4.14 by Archetype 3 (Developing aquaculture producers) and 2.84 by Archetype 1 (Emerging aquaculture producers). For example, aquaculture producers in Germany have expressed concerns that the country's pro-environment regulations prioritize ecological considerations over production realities (Lasner & Gimpel, 2024). Similarly, in the U.S., aquaculture expansion has been constrained by overlapping regulations across different institutional bodies (Jolly et al., 2023). Given that the aquaculture sector is often regulated by multiple agencies (Jolly et al., 2023), environmental regulations will negatively impact growth if pro-environment agencies have equal or higher power than pro-industry agencies (Naylor et al., 2023).

Developing aquaculture producers (Archetype 3) are the most negatively affected by TBTs. Despite being among the leading aquaculture producers, economies of scale do not appear to sufficiently mitigate the challenges associated with the significant fixed-cost investment associated with TBTs compliance. This likely stems from the limited availability of alternative production technologies, reflecting the pressing need for aquaculture production technology upgrades in these countries (Gentry et al., 2019; Partelow et al., 2025). Despite being generally characterized as having a lower level of production technology, Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1) experience a positive impact from TBTs. This could be due to technological advancements in seed supply and genetic resources, and improved credit access in some Archetype 1 countries, particularly coinciding with the study period (Jolly et al., 2023; Mapfumo, 2022).

Fig. 4: Effects of overall NTM, SPS, and TBT on aquaculture production output moderated by archetypes

Note: Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Results from moderation regressions with country-clustered standard errors. Control variables include population, GDP per capita, number of trade agreements, and applied MFN tariff rate.

Achieving long-term regulatory coherence of NTMs requires a bottom-up approach to designing standards and regulations. While Emerging aquaculture producers (Archetype 1) currently benefit from the positive production impacts of NTMs, their rapid growth might be temporary and will probably reach a natural limit (Gentry et al., 2019). In the long run, the inherent weaknesses in the more mature industries pose challenges for domestic producers in adapting to additional regulations, as seen in Developing and Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetypes 3 and 4). These findings underscore the need for policy frameworks tailored to each industry’s unique aquaculture contexts. At the same time, stronger collaboration between trade and consumer protection departments (typically responsible for formulating NTMs) and aquaculture departments is essential to harmonize trade regulations with sectoral development goals and capacities. This is particularly important in countries where aquaculture-related agencies are either absent or fragmented, such as Germany (Archetype 4) (Lasner & Gimpel, 2024) or several Latin American countries (Archetype 3) (Jolly et al., 2023).

Our findings also have implications for the biodiversity of farmed aquatic species. The technical and financial barriers posed by NTMs may further widen the gap between large-scale producers and small-scale producers, or those farming less commercially viable species within aquaculture

industries. While the former group can leverage economies of scale, the latter might struggle to maintain their operations. This could lead to the exclusion of the smallest producers and reduced access to common resources for other relevant stakeholders (Mialhe et al., 2018). Furthermore, this fragmentation of structure could result in over-intensification and monoculture systems, both of which are often linked to unsustainable use of land, water, and local aquatic biodiversity. As a relatively young sector, aquaculture has the opportunity to learn from past lessons of other terrestrial crop and animal industries and avoid similar pitfalls. Policies should therefore include diversifying farmed species and sustainable intensification alongside strengthening standards.

Our results must be interpreted with the following caveats. First, we use the count of NTMs as a proxy for a country's tendency to implement/ enforce such measures over time. While this approach provides an indication of a country's policy direction in addressing social and environmental issues in the aquaculture sector, it overlooks some important characteristics of NTMs, notably their specific contents. Future research can unpack these nuances to identify the most effective components of NTM regulations. Second, while we examine production output as a whole, we do not delve into how the industry structure changes. Finally, our approach does not capture the long-term effects of NTMs. For example, for Wealthy aquaculture producers (Archetype 4), the early adopters of NTMs, NTM impacts may have already materialized prior to the study period. The large standard errors of some coefficients may be attributed to the relatively short time frame of the dataset (11 years) and the limited within-country variation during that period (e.g., several EU countries exhibit only a single NTM change). Extending the timeline might offer a more thorough understanding of these dynamics.

2. Impact of aquaculture sustainability certification on mangrove cover

2.1. Descriptive statistics

In the Mekong Delta, the two predominant species groups applying for and receiving certification are shrimp and pangasius (respectively, at 2876 and 178 farm sites between 2012 and 2024), along with other less common groups, such as bivalves, tilapia, and tropical marine finfish (totaling 152 farm sites in the same period). While certified pangasius farm sites are located inland along the upstreams of the Mekong River, certified shrimp farm sites are distributed along the coastline and encroach on mangrove areas. Therefore, our analysis considers only the certified shrimp farm sites.

The treatment cells include only certified shrimp farms with statuses of “certified,” “expired,” “cancelled,” or “withdrawn,” as these statuses indicate that the farms have obtained certification. Another characteristic of these certified shrimp farms is their certificate type, which can be either “Single-site,” “Multi-site,” or “Group.” The year 2014 marked the emergence of the first two certified shrimp farms in the study area. This number gradually increased throughout the year (Fig. 5), peaking at 786 newly certified farm sites in 2022. However, our panel considers only the period up to 2020.

Fig. 5. Distribution of certified shrimp farm sites by the first certified year in the Mekong Delta between 2014-2024

Fig. 6 presents the average mangrove outcomes of treated and control 9-ha cells across three different periods 1990-1999, 2000-2009, and 2010-2020. The first period spans from the earliest year of available land-use data to 1999, which is the reference year set by ASC to assess the eligibility of farm locations for certification. The second period extends to 2010, the year ASC

was established – capturing the pre-certification phase. The third period extends to 2020, the final year of available land-use data. Before matching, treated cells show a substantially larger average mangrove area than the (unmatched) control cells consistently over time; this gap, however, becomes insignificant after matching. After matching, the covariate balance (the degree to which matching covariates are similar between the treated and control groups) becomes statistically indifferent, indicating that the two groups are comparable. We also observe i) a gradual decline in the average mangrove area over time: from over 2 ha in 1990-1999 to less than 1 ha in 2020, for every 9 ha; and ii) a notable increase in the treated group in the last three years of the study period. Fig. 6 shows a similar trend between the treated and control groups across the pre-treatment periods up until 2014 - the onset of the first certified shrimp farms, thus supporting the parallel trend assumption of Dif-in-dif estimators.

Fig. 6: Average mangrove area across 9-ha cells over time by treatment status

2.2. The impacts of certification on mangrove cover in Vietnam's Mekong Delta

Average impact

We first report the average impact of sustainability certification on the treated cells, using two-way fixed effects (TWFE) estimator described in Eq. (3). The estimated average treatment effects on the treated (ATT) suggest that exposure to aquaculture sustainability certification is positively associated with mangrove cover across the four spatial scales: 9 ha, 36 ha, 81 ha, and 225 ha. Table 7 (Columns 1, 3, 5, and 7) reports the results when all (neighbouring and non-neighbouring) control cells are considered. The increment in certification exposure (i.e., increase in the number of certified farms within a cell) increases mangrove area per cell from 0.12 ± 0.04 ha ($p < 0.01$) to 0.70 ± 0.40 ha ($p < 0.1$) as the scale increases from 9 ha to 81 ha (Table 7, Cols 1, 3, and 5). This relationship at the 225-ha scale is insignificant, although still positive (Table 7, Col 7). Given that our 9-ha samples include 803 treated cells, this translates to a total of approximately 96 ha of mangrove potentially being protected (using the coefficient from Col 1).

The observed increase in mangrove outcome may have biodiversity-meaningful implications. For instance, a study in Araca Bay, Brazil, found that even small mangrove fragments of roughly 500 m² could still enhance the taxonomic and functional biodiversity of macrobenthic invertebrates (Corte et al., 2021). However, most literature suggests that the functionality of biodiversity relies on the connectivity of mangrove habitats. Green et al. (2012) found that mangrove spatial configuration, such as patch isolation, shape index, and the number of mangroves within a 1 km radius, could significantly affect fish density and species richness; the more fragmented the mangroves, the lower the biodiversity. Similarly, disturbed mangrove areas were found to experience losses in benthic biodiversity, benthic biomass, and trophic resources (Carugati et al., 2018).

To assess whether and how certification affects the functionality of mangrove habitat, we use mangrove percentage (i.e., the proportion of mangrove areas relative to total land use areas within a unit cell) as a proxy, due to the lack of temporal variation of the current mangrove-affiliated biodiversity data. Our assumption is that if a cell contains a higher percentage of mangrove, the mangrove would be more connected and thus, may enhance the local biodiversity. We find similar results for the share of mangrove cover per cell. Our estimations indicate that exposure to certified shrimp farms are associated with a higher share of mangroves within treated cells; an additional certified farm might lead to a difference of 10% ($p < 0.01$) compared to control cells at the 9-ha scale. This magnitude is 9% ($p < 0.1$) at both the 36-ha and 81-ha scales, and is the lowest at 2% and statistically insignificant at the 225-ha scale.

Next, we check for potential treatment spillovers to the adjacent control cells. The strengthening of local environmental stewardship in one area, as reflected by an increase in mangrove area, could indicate that mangrove-destructive activities have been displaced to nearby locations. For instance, farmers (and/or their neighboring farmers) might rehabilitate mangrove within the treated cells while simultaneously expanding aquaculture production in the adjacent control cells, resulting in a reduction of mangrove areas in those areas. On the other hand, the proximity to the treated cells could yield positive spillovers as well. For example, neighboring farmers might begin to conduct mangrove rehabilitation in the adjacent control cells to be eligible for certification.

To account for this possibility, we exclude the potentially spatially biased control cells (i.e., those located directly next to treated cells) from the control group. Since we were unable to distinguish between additionality and spillover components from the estimated average effects within individual landscapes (cells), we rely on spillover patterns across cells to reflect on the plausibility of those within cells. If spillovers from certification exposure exist across cells, they are more likely to exist within each cell. At the 9-ha scale, the adjusted ATT (i.e., the difference in mangrove cover between treated and farther-away untreated, Table 7, Col 2) remains statistically significant. Compared with the earlier-reported ATTs (i.e., the difference between treated and all untreated, Col 1), the effect magnitude shows a slight increase. This means that the neighbor control cells have higher mangrove cover than the farther-away control cells, suggesting positive spillover from the treated 9-ha cells to the direct-neighbor control cells. If negative spillovers were to exist, they were offset by these positive spillovers. At the 81-ha scale, the adjusted ATT becomes smaller and loses significance (Table 7, Col 6 vs. Col 5), indicating that treated cells are statistically indistinguishable from farther-away controls. This implies that the direct-neighbor controls have significantly lower mangrove cover, pulling down the control

group mean (Col 5) and in turn hinting at a negative spillover at the 81-ha scale. However, if such displaced pressure were occurring, we should also observe it at the 225-ha scale. Because we do not, we cannot confirm such displaced pressure with the available data.

Table 7: Average ATTs of aquaculture sustainability certification on mangrove area and share across spatial scales

	Spatial scales							
	9 ha		36 ha		81 ha		225 ha	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Mangrove area per cell (ha)	0.12***	0.14***	0.34*	0.34*	0.70*	0.68	0.39	0.49
	(0.04)	(0.04)	(0.18)	(0.19)	(0.40)	(0.44)	(0.98)	(1.1)
Baseline mean (ha)	1.83	1.85	7.17	7.38	16.73	17.78	43.50	43.97
Mangrove share per cell (0-1, x100 for %)	0.01***	0.01***	0.009*	0.009*	0.009*	0.008	0.002	0.002
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.004)	(0.005)
Baseline mean (0-1, x100 for %)	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.22	0.19	0.20
Observations	140,585	137,733	54,994	49,693	32,705	27,652	15,872	10,788
Matched neighbour control cells	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Cell FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LULC control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Province-year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: Standard errors are clustered at cell level and reported in parentheses. Statistical significance: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. The equivalent resolutions are 9 ha (300x300m), 36 ha (600x600m), 81 ha (900x900m), and 225 ha (1.5x1.5km). Baseline means refer to the average mangrove cover (in hectares and percentage) of treated cells in 2000-2009. Matched samples including neighboring controls are shown in Columns 1, 3, 5, and 7, whereas those excluding neighboring controls are shown in Columns 2, 4, 6, and 8.

Dynamic effects

To better accommodate multiple groups and periods of heterogeneous treatment variable (i.e., exposure to increasing certified farms at different certification onset), we apply the intertemporal difference-in-differences estimator (Chaisemartin & D'Haultfœuille, 2024). Fig. 7 illustrates the dynamic effects of sustainability certification on mangrove areas for 7 years before and after certification onset for the finest and largest spatial scales of study.

Interestingly, we observe a significant increase in mangrove areas in the year just before certification at the 9-ha scale and in the year immediately following certification at both 9-ha and 225-ha scales. There is no significant gain in mangrove cover in years 2-3. Notably, in years 4-7, mangrove cover in treated 9-ha landscapes gains an additional area of 0.19 ± 0.07 ha in year 4 to 0.23 ± 0.08 ha in year 7 ($p < 0.01$). These findings suggest that the to-be-certified farms might be rehabilitating mangroves in the local area as part of the audit process before officially obtaining the certification. This pattern indicates pre-treatment anticipation and appears most pronounced only at the 9-ha scale.

Fig. 7: Dynamic effects of sustainability certification on mangrove area (hectare) in pre- and post-treatment periods at A) 9-ha and B) 225-ha scales

Note: a) Standard errors clustered at cell level. Error bars represent 95% CI. b) The treatment variable is the count of certified farm sites within a given cell. Control variables include cell- and year-fixed effects; areas of rice, other crops, urban, and other land uses. We apply Chaisemartin & D'Haultfœuille, 2024's `did_multiplegt_dyn` estimator, including only never-treated cells in our control groups.

One notable pattern from the dynamic effects of certification is the consistent positive, albeit largely insignificant, difference in mangrove outcomes between treated and control cells in the pre-treatment periods. Although this gap has been reduced and has become insignificant after controlling for different historical land use trends of cells and neighbouring cells (via excluding the direct neighbor control cells), the visible pre-treatment gap raises concerns about potential violations of the parallel-trend assumption.

To further validate our findings, we adopt the augmented synthetic control approach (Ben-Michael et al., 2021) to create synthetic controls that resemble the pre-treatment trend for each treated unit. Fig. 8 plots the estimated difference in mangrove area between treated and synthetic control cells over time. The qualitative pattern remains consistent; higher mangrove cover in the treated cells compared with synthetic control cells (year 3 in Fig. 8A, year 1 in Fig. 8B). The significance of the effect, however, is lower compared with the event-study coefficients.

A Resolution: 300x300m - Sample: Spatial matching - Treated: first year 2014-2017

B Resolution: 300x300m - Sample: Spatial matching - Treated: first year 2018-2020

Fig. 8: Estimated difference in mangrove area (hectare) between treated cells and synthetic control cells pre- and post-certification using Augmented Synthetic Control

Note: 90% CI in shaded region. Resolution 300x300m is equivalent to 9-ha. The synthetic controls are built based on donors from the unmatched sample and fit without covariates and control variables.

Overall, we find that mangrove-aquaculture landscapes exposed to the increasing presence of sustainability certification have larger mangrove cover than those that are never exposed to certification. Across four increasing landscape scales, only the finest scale (9 ha) consistently captures significant and positive mangrove outcomes, while the larger scales (36, 81, and 225 ha) largely show null effects. These patterns hold for two different DiD estimators and a synthetic control analysis. Regarding temporal aspects, significant mangrove gains can be observed in the first year after certification onset, both at the 9-ha and 225-ha scales, reflecting the short-term efforts to restore mangroves as compensation for certification. However, sustained mangrove conservation and protection in the long term can only be detected at the 9-ha scale. The contrasting significance patterns between the finest and largest spatial scales suggest that finer scales are more suitable for quantifying and monitoring mangrove restoration and conservation outcomes, whereas effects at larger scales may be diluted by other land use dynamics or simply lower levels of certification exposure.

However, three main limitations warrant further examination. First, the construction of our units of analysis is by no means perfect. Mangrove-aquaculture landscapes are generally considered a socio-spatial extent of a farmer network. Our current methodology, while providing a Delta-wide spatial coverage and a large set of biophysical and spatial covariates, is traded off for the loss of more nuanced socioeconomic aspects, such as land use rights, the distribution of earlier mangrove conservation projects, and participation in other certification schemes. Including these confounders could improve the credibility of counterfactuals, explain the heterogeneous effects in more nuance, and address the partial violation of the no anticipation assumption. Additionally, the current design of spatial units was chosen randomly based on the aggregation of common remote-sensing data of 30 m x 30 m resolution, serving as an exploratory approach and facilitating convenient data processing. To fully reflect the dynamics of society-ecology within landscapes across provinces, future research could redesign the spatial analysis units to match the average farm size in each province. Second, we have not addressed the within-cell spillover effects and disentangled their sources. Future studies could characterize the spillover mechanism by factoring in each sample landscape other elements of the local land-use dynamics and actors, for example, forest project management boards and industry actors. This may help clarify the indirect and spill-over effects shaping mangrove outcomes. Third, biodiversity impacts were not quantified using WP2 data because current biodiversity maps are largely derived from non-mangrove ecosystems, leading to high uncertainty for mangrove-specific estimates; future work would benefit from improved, mangrove-focused biodiversity datasets.

CONCLUSION

This report addresses T3.4 from two complementary angles – public regulatory and market-based governance. First, through the lens of national regulations, we analyze the role of standard-like non-tariff measures (NTMs) in synergizing aquaculture growth with the protection of consumers and the environment on a global scale. Second, we assess how voluntary market-based mechanisms, specifically aquaculture sustainability certification, contribute to protecting biodiversity-rich mangrove areas in the case study country of Vietnam.

Standard-like non-tariff measures, when used with legitimate regulatory objectives rather than protectionist tools, may reshape and enhance the quality and safety standards of aquaculture products, thereby strengthening consumer trust in the global aquatic food market. Our findings highlight the importance of incorporating aquaculture archetypes into the designs of trade policy instruments. The four archetypes, representing diverse trajectories of aquaculture development, shape how NTMs affect production output. While emerging aquaculture producers benefit most from the positive impacts of both sanitary and phytosanitary measures and technical barriers to trade, the inherent characteristics of the other archetypes hint at systemic barriers against effective compliance. The heterogeneity impact has an implication on resource management of farmed species; the potential risk of unintentionally promoting over-intensive farming practices where structural gaps exist particularly in the mature industries in wealthy and developing aquaculture producer countries.

Turning to aquaculture sustainability certification, we find a positive association between certification presence and mangrove outcomes in Vietnam’s Mekong Delta. Out of four spatial scales in our study, this pattern is particularly consistent for the smallest landscape scale of 9 hectares. This scale accordingly captures the additionality and perhaps also the positive spillovers. We do not negate the possibility of negative spillovers at this scale, but they were clearly outweighed by the other positive landscape-level effect components. Breaking down by time relative to the certification year, treated 9-ha cells retain more mangrove area around a year before the first official certification date and lasted for as long as seven years thereafter than they would have without certification. These findings fill an important gap in our understanding about the spatial impacts of aquaculture sustainability certification, which signals positive news for mangrove conservation but at the same time demonstrates yet limited effects at the landscape level. Besides, we need further evidence on the potential negative spillover effects at the larger landscape scales and their underlying sources; only if we could prove that the negative spillovers do not stem from certified farms can we conclude the overall effectiveness of sustainability certification. In sum, while aquaculture sustainability certification contributes to mangrove conservation, it cannot stand alone; complementary conservation efforts from multiple actors remain essential to achieve mangrove protection at larger scales.

This work contributes to the literature and the policy debate on environmental challenges in aquaculture in three key ways. First, it extends existing research on NTMs by examining their economic impact from a different perspective, specifically focusing on domestic production rather than imports/exports, which is extensively covered in the literature. Second, it offers new evidence regarding the role of governance in the aquaculture sector by demonstrating that the cause-effect relationships of these trade-related instruments in the aquatic biomass system are

complex. They vary through the interplay of multiple factors, including socioeconomic conditions, environmental performance, and regulatory quality. This underscores the importance of designing thoughtful, coherent, and context-sensitive policies tailored to specific producer archetypes. Third, to our knowledge, the certification-mangrove analysis is the first study to investigate the environmental impacts of aquaculture certification at the landscape level. This represents the collective spatial impact of sustainability certification, enabling international trade to positively impact the environment at distant production sites.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This report contributes the following points to the project:

- Expand the database with aquaculture statistics, production sites, and governance measures
- Conceptualize how sustainable aquaculture expansion, as governed by non-tariff measures and aquaculture sustainability certification, contributes to mitigating the sea-related biodiversity threats
- Provide empirical evidence for the role of aquaculture-specific contexts in determining how non-tariff measures affect production output
- Provide counterfactual-based evidence for the landscape-level biodiversity impacts of aquaculture sustainability certification, using mangrove cover as a proxy

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APPENDIX

Figure A1: Potential mechanisms of aquaculture sustainability certification effects on mangrove cover within a spatial unit

Note: a) Baseline condition refers to the mangrove cover before the cutoff dates for certification eligibility. b) Additionality refers to the changes on mangrove cover within the certified areas. c) Direct spillovers may be positive if certification holders restore mangrove on other lands they own outside the certified farm. Direct spillover may be negative if certification holders clear mangrove elsewhere as a result of the improved livelihoods induced by certification. d) Indirect spillovers may be positive if the social norms and practices of neighbouring farms become more pro-mangrove through exposure to certification. They may be negative if the perceived success of certified farms induces expansion of aquaculture by new and old producers at the cost of mangrove. e&f) Permanence refers to the lasting sustainable behaviors, thus maining mangrove cover, even in the absence of incentives; non-permanence refers to the opposite scenario. Increasing or decreasing the scale of spatial unit of analysis can accumulate more or fewer certified farms and even non-certified farms and other land uses, thus altering the magnitude and sign of net landscape-level effect. Icons are sourced from Microsoft Office and Keesey (2025)⁶.

⁶ Keesey, M. (2025). Phylopic - An open database of freely reusable silhouettes of life forms. <https://www.phylopic.org/>

